

COMMUNICATION BETWEEN A TEACHER AND PUPILS AS AN EXCHANGE OF SPIRITUAL VALUES

Azimova Ziyoda Ergashevna

Republic of Uzbekistan, Andijan city Dean of the Faculty of Preschool Education,
Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Gulrukh Zulunova Bobirmirzo kizi

Student of Andijan State University, Faculty of Pedagogy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6678118>

Abstract. *This article details communication between a teacher and pupils as an exchange of spiritual values, Innovation methods of teaching as part of the academic process.*

Key words: *communication, spiritual values, scientific knowledge, cooperative pedagogy, pedagogical communication.*

ОБЩЕНИЕ УЧИТЕЛЯ И УЧЕНИКОВ КАК ОБМЕН ДУХОВНЫМИ ЦЕННОСТЯМИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье подробно рассматривается общение учителя и учеников как обмен духовными ценностями, инновационные методы обучения как часть учебного процесса.*

Ключевые слова: *общение, духовные ценности, научное познание, кооперативная педагогика, педагогическое общение.*

INTRODUCTION

Communication pedagogy is a new branch of scientific knowledge, standing at the intersection of social psychology and humanistic pedagogy. Its emergence is due to the logic of the development of world psychological and pedagogical thought.

Only since the second half of the 1980s, with the beginning of the democratic reorganization of our society, does pedagogical freethinking take on real contours. An expression of an organized protest of creative teachers against the dominance of a soulless administrative-command pedagogy was an innovative movement and the pedagogy of cooperation gained support.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The core of this concept was the equal partnership and humanity of pedagogical communication, the construction of the educational process in universities. The term "collaborative pedagogy" proposed by innovative educators has gained wide popularity.

However, it is precisely this that makes it possible to characterize the educational interaction, its structure, and functions in a more comprehensive manner. Close to it in foreign science are the concepts of "cooperative pedagogy", "groupism", "communicative pedagogy", "dialogue pedagogy".

Initially, communication is a basic category of social psychology. It is defined as the interaction of two or more people, which consists in the exchange of cognitive, emotional and evaluative information. Communication is included in practical interaction - teaching, work, ensuring its planning, implementation and control. Since the end of the 60s, the concept of "pedagogical communication" has appeared at the intersection of social and pedagogical psychology.

The aesthetic block includes the following skills: to introduce students to a high culture of communication, to be artistic, expressive, to activate the emotional tone of students, to introduce them to a high culture of communication. The structure of the technological block includes skills: to use teaching and educational tools, methods, techniques, a variety of forms of interaction, to choose the optimal style of communication management, to observe pedagogical tact.

RESULTS

Pedagogical science is characterized by a much broader interpretation of educational interaction, which goes far beyond the psychological framework. It is designed to develop such important aspects of it as moral and ethical, aesthetic, technological.

Based on the psychological definition of communication "as information and subject interaction" in the holistic process of pedagogical communication, it is possible to single out the communicative and subject aspects. They are organically linked.

Subject interaction generates communicative. The latter, in turn, ensures the productivity of the former. Confidential communication allows the exchange of personal spiritual values. Students and pupils experience a deficit of just such communication.

Subject interaction is more developed in theoretical and practical terms. Communicative interaction in pedagogy is still not given due attention. Pedagogical communication is a broad concept that includes all the variety of teacher communications not only with students, but also with colleagues and administration.

DISCUSSION

In the holistic process of pedagogical communication, didactic and communicative aspects were identified for the first time. The process of pedagogical communication has an internal and external side. Psychology focuses on the first, and pedagogy on the second. Pedagogical theory and practice are also interested in the mental processes that take place between the teacher and the student, and how to manage them.

Subject didactic interaction is focused on the formation of a system of knowledge, skills and abilities among students. The content of communicative interaction is the exchange of thoughts, views, interests, feelings, moods in connection with subject interaction.

The teacher and the student can enter into substantive interaction in the classroom, in preparation for conferences, and work in the student scientific society. However, the pedagogical effect of this interaction is determined not only by the nature and method of organizing the leading activity - cognitive, artistic, labor, but also by the communicative interaction of the educator with pupils.

The dominant functions of communicative interaction are educational. A clear indicator of successful communicative interaction between a teacher and a student is a favorable moral and psychological climate in the classroom.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the socio-psychological block includes the ability to dispose students to communication, to make a favorable impression, to understand the uniqueness of the personality of each student. The structure of the moral and ethical block includes the ability to build communication on a humane, democratic basis, be guided by the principles and rules of professional ethics and etiquette, and initiate a favorable moral climate for communication.

References:

1. Berezovin, N.A. Problems of pedagogical communication: teaching aid / N.A. Berezovin. - Minsk: University Publishing House, 2001.
2. Hills, P. Teaching learning as communication process / P. Hills. – London: Groom Helm. 2004.
3. Rydanova, I.I. Fundamentals of pedagogy of communication / I.I. Rydanov. - Minsk: Belarusian Navuka, 2003.
4. Leontiev, A.A. Psychology of communication: textbook / A.A. Leontiev. – Tartu: Publishing House of the University of Tartu. 2002.
5. Kan-Kalik, V.A. Teacher about pedagogical communication / V.A. Kan-Kalik. – M.: Enlightenment, 2000.